

THE BASIC CONSTITUENTS OF GAS-TAR

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In search for a source of β - and γ -picoline, the basic fraction of the light oil of the tar supplied by the Oriental Gas Company, Calcutta, was subjected to fractional distillation in a specially devised double Gan's column (1 m. long). The fraction boiling at 90° - 170° was fractionated repeatedly until constant fractions were obtained. In all 12 fractionations were made. From 5 gallons of crude pyridine, 18 lbs. of pyridine (112° - 118°), 6 lbs. of α -picoline (126° - 132°), 8 lbs. of β -picoline (140° - 147°), 4 lbs. of 2:4-lutidine (152° - 158°), 8 lbs. of a residue boiling above 160° and about 6 lbs. of total intermediate fractions were obtained.

The β -picoline fraction usually contains a mixture of β -picoline, γ -picoline and 2:6-lutidine. Attempts were therefore made to separate the constituents by employing methods based on the difference in solubility of the complex salts formed by oxalic acid (Lidstone, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 241) and zinc chloride (*Annalen*, 1920, 420, 192, 197; U. S. P. 2, 456, 773/1948; *Chem. Abs.*, 1949, 43, 2240). No trace of γ -picoline or 2:6-lutidine could be obtained after repeated trials. The " β -picoline" fraction was then oxidised by potassium permanganate when nicotinic acid (m. p. 228°) was obtained in a fairly good yield. It is concluded that the β -picoline fraction from gas tar does not contain any γ -picoline nor any 2:6-lutidine. Attempts were next made to oxidise 2:4-lutidine fraction into 2:4-lutidinic acid and to convert the latter into 4-pyridine carboxylic acid or isonicotinic acid.

Oxidation of " β -Picotine" fraction by KMnO_4 .—A mixture of the " β -picoline" fraction (200 g.) and water ($2\frac{1}{2}$ litres) was heated on the water-bath under reflux and stirred while powdered KMnO_4 (900 g.) was added in portions of 20 g. during 6 hours. After the last charge of the permanganate had been decolorised, the hot reaction mixture was filtered by suction. The manganese dioxide was washed twice with hot water. The combined filtrate was concentrated to 3000 c.c. and set at p_H 3-4 with about 260 c.c. of HCl. The slurry was heated up to 95° - 100° to dissolve the voluminous precipitate and allowed to cool slowly at room temperature. The purpose of slow cooling was to avoid contamination with potassium chloride. The nicotinic acid, thus obtained, was filtered off and washed with a little cold water. The filtrate was again concentrated and cooled to 5° , when a second crop of nicotinic acid was obtained. Total yield was 60%.

Oxidation of 2:4-Lutidine fraction by KMnO_4 to 2:4-Lutidinic Acid and Conversion to isoNicotinic Acid.—2:4-Lutidine fraction (100 g.) was heated on a water-bath and stirred with a solution of KMnO_4 (300 g.) in 2000 c.c. water till the colour was discharged (6 hours). A further equal amount of KMnO_4 in 500 c.c. water was then added and the heating continued till the liquid again was decolorised (12 hours). The reaction mixture was filtered hot. The precipitate of manganese dioxide was twice washed with hot water and filtered. The combined filtrate was evaporated to $1/3$

volume, acidified to litmus with H_2SO_4 (dil.) and evaporated to crystallisation. An equal volume of alcohol was then added. The filtrate from the precipitated potassium sulphate was diluted with water (1000 c.c.) and warmed, and 2:4-lutidinic acid precipitated as the silver salt by addition of dilute silver nitrate solution. The precipitate was washed with warm water, suspended in hot water and decomposed by H_2S . 2:4-Lutidinic acid separated from the filtrate on evaporation, followed by cooling. The dried acid was heated above its melting point under diminished pressure (250 mm.) when there was a rapid evolution of carbon dioxide and *isonicotinic* acid sublimed on the upper part of the flask; m. p. 317° , yield 50 g.

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